

Deliverable 3.1

Workpackage 3

Responsible Partner: 36-INSA

Contributing partners: 13-SSI

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP3.1

Database of zoonotic *Clostridium difficile* isolates across participant countries (task 3.1)

Description of the task

There is increasing evidence that *C. difficile* may have a foodborne or zoonotic aetiology and has also been suggested as a reservoir/receptor of resistance genes that might be transferred to other species in the host gut as well as in the environment. In task **JRP15-R2-WP3-T1** the task leader (Mónica Oleastro, 36-INSA), her deputy leader (Søren Persson, 13-SSI) and other WP3 participants aimed at investigating the epidemiology of zoonotic *C. difficile* through the identification zoonotic types of *C. difficile* across the WP3 countries by generating an epidemiological survey of zoonotic ribotypes. The task started in M25 at the kick-off meeting and finished in M36 and comprised a collection of genomic data (WGS reads) and associated metadata by the consortium partners on potential zoonotic types of toxigenic *C. difficile* isolates from various sources (human, animal and environment). Metadata included demographic and epidemiological data, as well as strain type, namely ribotype, toxin profile and AMR profile, when available. Discrimination between zoonotic and non-zoonotic types was based on *C. difficile* ribotypes and other genetic markers described in the literature.

Description of deliverable

In M25, each participant partner started a sampling campaign in order to enrich the collection of *C. difficile* isolates available from different sources, more specifically from diverse animal and environmental sources. Until now, *C. difficile* isolates have been obtained from reptiles, lamas, poultry carcass, pets, pigs, food and manure. Due to COVID pandemic, the sampling will be extended until April 2021.

Prior to the selection of zoonotic types among the human isolates, an exhaustive search was made in the peer-reviewed literature. The inventory of the zoonotic types was uploaded in the project site.

Based on this inventory, each partner has selected the human isolates from zoonotic types, from the existing collections, isolated between 2016-2020. The overall set of *C. difficile* isolates from different sources was used for the construction of the database. The first version of the database was uploaded in the project site (see **Annex 1** to this deliverable). This database will be updated when necessary. A harmonized protocol for *C. difficile* isolation and characterization was developed by WP3 partners (**Annex 2**).